
INDUSTRY 4.0 READINESS OF PACKAGING TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION IN INDIA**Ms. Nisha Padmanabhan**

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ABSTRACT

Any industry in today's age is working towards its development through innovation and sustainability. Early 21st century started with the Industry 4.0 - Cyber-Physical Age, and Packaging industry is being highly influenced by it. The Industry 4.0 technologies such as automation, smart manufacturing systems, digital quality control, and data-driven decision-making has become an integral part of Packaging Industry for some time now. As a result of the developments in the industry, skill requirements for packaging professionals gets reshaped very often. This change is challenging traditional models of technical education. In 2020, The ministry of Education came with the first education policy of 21st century, National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 for Indian Educational transformation which concentrates on industry relevance, skill-oriented learning, and future-ready curricula. However, it's important that we evaluate if the current syllabus aligns with the industry requirements or not.

This paper examines the Industry 4.0 readiness of undergraduate Packaging Technology education in India through a syllabus-level analysis of an autonomous undergraduate program as the primary case study, supported by benchmarking against other curricular practices across other institutions in India. A structured Industry 4.0 competency framework is used to assess automation awareness, systems-level understanding, digital tools, data analytics, smart inspection, and connectivity, while also examining how NEP 2020 objectives are reflected in curriculum design.

The findings indicate that Packaging Technology education in India demonstrates strong foundational and practical strengths but remains partially aligned with Industry 4.0 requirements. The autonomous program analyzed performs better than many equivalent institutes due to its practical depth and curricular flexibility, yet Industry 4.0 integration remains largely implicit. The paper concludes by identifying focused curriculum enhancements necessary to strengthen Industry 4.0 readiness while supporting NEP 2020's vision of future-oriented technical education.

Keywords: *Packaging Technology, Industry 4.0, NEP 2020, Curriculum Evaluation, Higher Education*

1. INTRODUCTION

Packaging education in India has been growing and many colleges have started with courses that has the capacity to support the industry in supply of labour. In India, packaging education happens in 3 levels. The diploma level which any student who have completed their SSC can join. The degree level wherein students can join after completing their 12th or diploma course. And post-graduation in which student can join after completing graduation. Apart from this there are many certificate courses in packaging Technology. These courses are built keeping in mind the industry requirements. The industry sector considered while building the courses are food processing, pharmaceuticals, FMCG and other packaging industries.

The undergraduate courses, mainly focuses on packaging materials, production processes, operations of machinery and quality aspects of the industry. However, modern packaging plants have evolved into automated, interconnected, and digitally monitored systems. Industry 4.0 technologies—such as smart machinery, machine vision inspection, sensor-based monitoring, and real-time data analytics—have become integral to packaging operations. Consequently, packaging professionals are now expected to possess system-level understanding and digital awareness in addition to conventional technical skills.

Simultaneously, NEP 2020 calls for higher education curricula that are flexible, skill-based, multidisciplinary, and aligned with industry needs. For applied technical disciplines such as Packaging Technology, Industry 4.0 provides a practical technological pathway to realize NEP's educational vision. This paper therefore examines the readiness of Packaging Technology education in India to address Industry 4.0 requirements within the broader policy context.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Policy Context:

University Education Commission (1948-1949)

The Radhakrishnan Commission focussed on improving university education quality. It emphasised on liberal education and building academic standards. Teachers training and research was another focal point of this commission.

This commission had very limited focus on applied skills, industrial technologies or even manufacturing needs.

Secondary Education Commission (1952-1953)

The Mudaliar Commission focussed on reforming secondary education, introducing vocational education at school level. A board-based curriculum started.

This commission was one of the earliest recognitions to vocational education however, failed to form a structured pathway for higher education in technical fields.

National Policy on Education (1968)

The NPE of 1968 focussed on equal access to education. It emphasised on science and mathematics more, also leading to expansion of technical and higher educations.

This policy strengthened engineering and many technical institutes. Its major focus was on manpower creation, due to the demand of industry. However, the alignment with industry was indirect, hence curriculum modernization was not done in the pace the industry was growing. The policy failed to focus on employability.

National Policy on Education (1986)

In 1986, NPE concentrated more on vocational education, education reforms for teachers, using technology for education, and expanding technical institutes.

This policy encouraged industry-oriented, applied and vocational courses. This policy had technology integration, but in a basic form. It wasn't responsive to the rapid changes of the industry.

Programme of Action (1992)

This was a modified version of 1986 NPE. This policy implemented the framework of NPE 1986. It helped in institutional strengthening by improving quality and access.

It helped professional education and focused on strengthening polytechnical courses. However, it concentrated more on infrastructure and curriculum agility was overlooked. It failed to incorporate digital manufacturing and smart systems.

Technical Education Reforms (1990s-2010s)

AICTE led this policy and created standards to technical curriculum. Industry interaction, accreditation and quality assurance were some of the benefits of this policy.

This policy promoted laboratory and practical approach. It also introduced OBE – outcome-based education system. The curricula did remain discipline-centric, still remained slow to adapt to the new technologies.

Skill Development Policies (Pre 2009)

This policy was employability-centric. Major focus was on workforce readiness with the participation of industry in training the workforce.

This policy had limited integration with university curricula's and often operated parallel to the formal degree level education.

NEP 2020 and Technical Education

NEP 2020 represents a shift from content-heavy curricula toward outcome-oriented, skill-driven, and industry-aligned education. Key policy objectives relevant to technical programs include:

- Emphasis on experiential and skill-based learning
- Stronger industry–academia linkage
- Integration of emerging technologies
- Curriculum flexibility and future readiness

Although NEP 2020 does not explicitly mandate Industry 4.0 adoption, its emphasis on employability and relevance implicitly requires alignment with contemporary industrial practices. For Packaging Technology education, Industry 4.0 therefore becomes a critical enabler of NEP 2020 objectives.

2.2 Industrial Revolution

Industry 1.0 – Mechanization (Approx. 1760 – 1840)

This era marks the birth of manufacturing as an organized activity of industry. It was the introduction of mechanical production, where a clear transition was seen from handcrafts to machine-based work.

The workforce skills required were basic machine operation and mechanical handling ability.

Industry 2.0 – Mass Production (Approx. 1870 – 1960)

During this time, electric power use started. Thus, introducing assembly lines. Industries like automotive, packaging and consumer goods started to scale rapidly due to standardization and mass production.

The workforce skills required were machine handling, repetitive task execution and basic technical supervision.

Industry 3.0 – Automation & Digitalization (Approx. 1970 – 2010)

Electronics and IT were introduced during this period. Automation of both machines and processes by controlling and monitoring with the help of computers became common.

Small scale plants in India still operate at this level. The workforce skills like technical operation of automated systems, process monitoring, basic programming and troubleshooting are required.

Industry 4.0 – Smart Manufacturing (Approx. 2010 – Present)

Intelligent and connected manufacturing improved the real time data exchange. This was possible due to the integration of physical and digital systems. Industry 4.0 shifted the manufacturing from merely automated factories to intelligent and self-optimizing systems.

Workers need to have skills like, system thinking, data interpreting, digital literacy and cross-disciplinary collaborations.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Sources

- **Primary data:** Only syllabus review of a B.Sc. Packaging Technology program offered by an autonomous college (Semesters I–VI). The syllabus document included the proposed theory courses, laboratory components, programming, and industrial training to be applied during the course as per their BOS.
- **Secondary data:** General review of undergraduate Packaging Technology and Printing & Packaging curricula across Indian universities and autonomous colleges, used only for contextual benchmarking. This only included data which was available online as part of the marketing documents of the courses other institutes are running.

The study is limited to **curriculum content and structure**, excluding infrastructure, faculty profile, teaching structure, placement data and students capability alterations before and after the course.

3.2 Industry 4.0 Evaluation Framework for Packaging Industry

Industry 4.0 readiness was assessed using the following parameters:

1. Packaging fundamentals (baseline competence)
2. Machinery and systems-level understanding
3. Automation awareness
4. Digital manufacturing and software exposure
5. Data analytics application
6. AI and machine vision (conceptual exposure)
7. Connectivity and smart systems

Each parameter was graded on a four-point scale (A–D), reflecting the level of explicit and applied Industry 4.0 integration.

4. Analysis

4.1 Overview of Packaging Technology Education in India

Across Indian institutions, Packaging Technology education exhibits strong disciplinary foundations:

- Detailed coverage of packaging materials and structures
- Emphasis on machinery operation and laboratory work
- Manual testing and conventional quality control

However, benchmarking indicates that:

- Automation is often taught theoretically
- Digital manufacturing concepts are minutely integrated
- Data-driven quality and smart systems are largely absent

As a result, most programs remain aligned with **Industry 3.0 manufacturing model**, despite operating within a policy environment encouraging future-oriented skills.

4.2 Case Study: Industry 4.0 Readiness of an Autonomous Program

Strengths

The autonomous program evaluated demonstrates:

- Strong system-oriented machinery education
- Extensive laboratory and practical exposure
- Introduction of programming (Python), indicating digital intent
- Mandatory industrial training supporting experiential learning

These features align well with NEP 2020’s emphasis on skills and industry relevance and position the program ahead of many traditional Packaging Technology curricula.

Gaps in Industry 4.0 Integration

Despite these strengths:

- Automation is addressed mechanically rather than digitally
- Programming is not contextualized using packaging production or quality data
- Quality control remains predominantly test-based
- Smart manufacturing concepts such as sensors, connectivity, and real-time analytics are absent

Industry 4.0 integration therefore remains **implicit rather than applied**.

4.3 Comparative Industry 4.0 Readiness

Dimension	Case Institution	Typical Indian Programs
Packaging fundamentals	Strong	Strong
Experiential learning (NEP)	High	Moderate
Systems-level machinery understanding	High	Moderate
Automation awareness	Moderate	Low
Digital manufacturing	Limited	Minimal
Data-driven quality	Absent	Absent
Overall Industry 4.0 readiness	Moderate	Low–Moderate

5. DISCUSSION

From the analysis it is clear that a gap lies between policy intent and technological implementation. Even though NEP 2020 has given structural flexibility and encouraged skill-based education, the Industry 4.0 integration has not been fully adapted within Packaging Technology curricula. The autonomous program studied illustrates readiness for transformation, but without specific digital and system-level integration, graduates may remain underprepared for smart packaging environments.

Industry 4.0 should be viewed as a natural extension of packaging education and not an external addition.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Industry 5.0 is already emerging now (early 2020s) and growing fast. This is a Human centric, sustainability and resilience phase. Soon Human-machine synergy will become a new normal. Education system has to make changes so that it can be equipped to serve the industrial requirements of the future. Following are the recommendations with respect to changes that need to be implemented soon,

- Embedding Industry 4.0 concepts within existing machinery and quality courses is necessary.
- Programming must be context through packaging related data rather than generalization.
- Digital inspection and smart quality systems must be introduced in curriculum.
- Align industrial training with observation of automation and digital practices

These enhancements support NEP 2020 objectives while improving Industry 4.0 readiness without requiring major curriculum restructuring.

6. CONCLUSION

Fundamentally strong courses also need to be checked with respect to the requirements of Industry. The Packaging Technology education in India is well built in fundamental knowledge and practical alignment but has to improve as per the standards of Industry 4.0. Due to the experiential depth and flexibility in the curriculum of the autonomous program it performs better than many equivalent institutes, however, Industry 4.0 integration remains limited. It is essential that measures be taken to strengthen Industry 4.0 readiness within the NEP 2020 framework to ensure that Packaging Technology graduates are prepared for the evolving demands of modern manufacturing industries.

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